

The Spatio-Temporal GISystem for the Studies of the Service Lists of the Chinese Maritime Customs Service, 1875-1948

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Abstract: The Service Lists compiled by the Statistical Department of the Inspectorate General of Customs started from 1875 and ended in 1948. The Service Lists stated over 24000 staff members' information, namely name, birthplace, station, nationality, promotion, etc. These staff members were from more than two dozens of nationalities so the Service Lists were probably the most explicit and fruitful records for this internationalized staff in modern history.

Historians have been aware of this vault since the late 19th century but the scale of this set is too vast to research. Since the beginning of the 21st century, the digital database technologies allow historians to research this set to a deeper extent. Hans van de Ven and Robert Bickers have finished an Access database for all staff members. Nowadays, the online spatio-temporal database and GISystem could push the studies of this set a step further. This article discusses the latest design of the database and the trouble shooting of the construction of which. Then this article also turns to how this database could reflect on the visualization of the staff members' transfers and promotions on maps and how new personnel records can be generated from the database.

Keywords: Chinese Maritime Customs Service, Statistical Department, Service List, GISystem

1. Introduction

The staff members of the Chinese Maritime Customs Service (CMCS) were over 22,000. They were spread at 47 Custom Houses in the Chinese mainland, Korean peninsula and two ones in Taiwan, as well as the London Office in London. Apart from the various spatial attributes the variety of the staff was also vast: over 23 nationalities, 21 birth provinces (only for the Chinese staff), and spoke 11 languages and 15 dialects (only for the Chinese staff).² The Inspectorate General of Customs had four Departments, namely Revenue, Marine, Education (better known as Tongwenguan) and Postal (better known as Youzhengju),³ and each Department had 3-6 sections.⁴ In addition to all the aforesaid standing attributes, some more information also occasionally occurred in the *Service Lists*, such as staff members' educational certificates, Chinese official ranks, titles of honour, decorations, etc.

The data of the CMCS *Service Lists* has always been the most explicit, continuous and consistent set for studying personnel and institutional history throughout the Qing, Northern, Nationalist and Wang Jingwei collaborationist governments' rules. However, the scale of this data is beyond traditional historiography to cope with. Historians in Mainland China have been trying to apply traditional methodology but their studies only can cover a part of the complete picture of the CMCS staff.

Thus, this data requires database for administration and GISystem for visualization, but for CMCS historians, the complexity and scale of this data would take their years' of studies. Needless to say GISystem programmers would find it unlikely to design an appropriate database to fit in such set of data.

This article then aims to discuss how historians should adapt the *Service Lists*' original metadata to a standardized database format for GISystem. This adaptation for standardization can be discussed in two phases: the Cambridge-Bristol joint project in 2002 and the SJTU project in 2018.

The standardization of the metadata would confront a number of issues and how historians now and twenty years ago cope with these issues.

The second issue this article aims to discuss is that how the design of this database can be more applicable to other studies of historical personnel. The author likes to propose a new design of online database – the database should include the 'fixed information' and 'unfixed information' for every staff member. Then the temporal changes of staff, such as station, rank, post, etc. can all be reflected on this category.

This article first discusses 1) the 74 issues *Service Lists*' historical issues, 2) explains how the Bristol CMCS project designed an Access offline database for the CMCS staff, 3) the new design of this database, and 4) the GISystem visualization of the new database.

2. The Editorial Changes over the 74-Year Service List's

Because since 1875 the inspectorate started to compile the *Service List* till 1948. The 74-year set had a serial editorial changes, errors and inconsistency between Chinese and English versions. For programmers, the standardization of data format is necessary but the aforesaid difficulties are the first obstacle.

2.1 The Inauguration of Service List

² From 1876-1880, the *Service Lists* only had three dialects, namely Canton, Ningpo and Fukien. Since 1881, the *Service Lists* had ten dialects, namely Amoy, Canton, Foochow, Nanking (Southern Mandarin), Peking (Northern Mandarin), Ningpo, Swatow, Shanghai, Japanese, Malay. Since 1901, the CMCS finalized its dialect categorization and listed 15 ones: Canton, Hakka, Swatow, Amoy, Foochow, Wenchow, Ningpo, Kinhua, Shanghai/Soochow, Hangchow, Huichow, Yangchow, Northern Mandarin, Southern Mandarin and Western Mandarin. See CAI Cheng and CHANG Chihyun, "Fangyan yu Wanqing Haiguan Tongwen Gongshi Shujuku Yanjiu: 1876-1911" (The Database Studies for Dialects and the CMCS Chinese Clerks, 1876-1911), *Journal of Chinese Social and Economic History* 2 (2021): 46-61.

³ According to the *Service Lists*, the Inspectorate General of Customs only had the Revenue and Marine Departments from 1875-1887. The Inspectorate added the Educational Department, better known as *Tongwenguan* (Interpreter School) in Peking and Canton in 1887, and added the Postal Department in 1896.

⁴ Under each Department, there were sub-sections but there was no standardized names for them. The ones under the Revenue Department were the Indoor Staff, Outdoor Staff and Marine Staff and under the Marine Department were Engineers, Harbours and Lights in the 1st-Issue *Service List* of 1875.

² From 1876-1880, the *Service Lists* only had three dialects, namely Canton, Ningpo and Fukien. Since 1881, the *Service Lists* had ten dialects, namely Amoy, Canton, Foochow, Nanking (Southern Mandarin), Peking (Northern Mandarin), Ningpo, Swatow, Shanghai, Japanese, Malay. Since 1901, the CMCS finalized its dialect categorization and listed 15 ones: Canton, Hakka, Swatow, Amoy, Foochow, Wenchow, Ningpo, Kinhua, Shanghai/Soochow, Hangchow, Huichow, Yangchow, Northern Mandarin, Southern Mandarin and Western Mandarin. See CAI Cheng and CHANG Chihyun, "Fangyan yu Wanqing Haiguan Tongwen Gongshi Shujuku Yanjiu: 1876-1911" (The Database Studies for Dialects and the CMCS Chinese Clerks, 1876-1911), *Journal of Chinese Social and Economic History* 2 (2021): 46-61.

Although the Inspectorate General of Customs inaugurated in 1854, the CMCS had not published any *Service List* from 1854-1874. The 1st-Issue *Service List* was published in 1875 for the list of the CMCS staff from August 1874-August 1875 but it did not have the Chinese staff and the ‘station’ so we could not know where the staff members stationed.

220 ANNUAL REPORTS, 1874.

Date of Appointment to present Rank.	Years previously served.	NAME.	Nationality.	Date of Last Appointment.
1852, Dec.	1 1/2	T. Dick.	British.	1861, June.
1865, March	5 1/2	A. Macpherson.	"	1859, Oct.
" Nov.	6 1/2	F. W. White.	"	" Aug.
1867, Aug.	4 1/2	F. Kleinwachter.	German.	1865, Feb.
" Oct.	8	F. E. Wright (Audit Secretary, I. G.).	British.	1859, Oct.
1868, March	5 1/2	H. Kopsch.	"	1865, Jany.
" June	2 1/2	Edw'd. B. Drew.	American.	1865, Oct.
" 5 1/2	J. Alex. Man.	British.	1865, Feb.	
1872, March	6 1/2	G. Dotring.	German.	1867, July.
" Oct.	5 1/2	James H. Hart.	British.	1865, April.
" Nov.	7 1/2	J. D. Campbell* (Non-Resident Secretary, I. G.).	American.	1865, Aug.
" 7 1/2	F. E. Woodruff.	British.	1865, Nov.	
1873, Jany.	9 1/2	W. Clewright (Chinese Secretary, I. G.).	British.	1865, April.
" April	10 1/2	H. E. Holson.	American.	1865, Aug.
" July	4 1/2	A. Huber.	French.	1869, April.
" Sept.	—	Robt. E. Breslon (Chief Secretary, I. G., detached).	British.	1873, Sept.
" Oct.	8 1/2	E. C. Taintor (Statistical Secretary, I. G.).	American.	1865, Aug.
1874, Jany.	14 1/2	J. L. Hammond.	British.	1859, May.
" Oct.	10	H. O. Brown.	British.	1864, Oct.
1875, April	13 1/2	A. Novion.	French.	1865, Jany.
DEPUTY COMMISSIONERS.				
副稅務司				
1867, July	3 1/2	G. H. Noetzel.†	Swiss.	1865, Nov.
1873, March	11 1/2	C. L. Simpson.	British.	1861, May.
" 10 1/2	J. Smith† (Assistant Audit Secretary, I. G.).	British.	1862, Sept.	
1874, April	13 1/2	Colin Jamieson† (Acting Chief Secretary, I.G.).	British.	1866, Jany.
" 1 1/2	E. McKean.	British.	1874, March.	
" Nov.	3 1/2	J. McLeary Brown.	British.	1873, April.

* Retired and rejoined. † The officiated as Acting Commissioner or Assistant-in-charge. ‡ Including Rates Service.

Source: *Service List*, 1st Issue (1875), p. 2.
Figure 1: The 1st-Issue Service List of 1875

The 2nd-issue then had the list of Chinese staff (at that time, there was no Chinese Assistants but only Clerks). With the ‘date of first appointment’. The latter information was extremely crucial as we can estimate how many employees the CMCS had recruited from 1854-1875.

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4th.—CHINESE STAFF.

Date of Appointment to present Rank.	Years previously served.	NAME.	Monthly Pay.	Birth-place.	Dialects spoken.	Date of Last Appointment.	Station.
CLERKS. (76).							
Principal Clerks: 5.							
1876, April	20 1/2	Tsui Wan.	200	Maaco.	Canton, Ningpo.	1855, Oct.	Shanghai.
" "	17 1/2	L. Wong.	175	Kwangtung.	" " Fokien.	1859, Jany.	Foochow.
" "	16 1/2	Tang Chek Hing.	150	do	" "	1860, "	Kiangsi.
" "	14 1/2	Chung An.	125	do	" "	1861, May	Chiao.
" "	11 1/2	Lim Chingwan.	115	Peang.	" Fokien.	1864, Sept.	Assy.
First Clerks: 20.							
1876, April	15	C. K. Tong.	100	Kwangtung.	Ningpo.	1861, April	Shanghai.
" "	14 1/2	Wong Wai.	100	Kwangtung.	Canton, Fokien.	" Jany.	Canton.
" "	14 1/2	Chow Kwae Kway.	100	Kiangsi.	Ningpo.	" "	Hankow.
" "	13 1/2	Wong Kam Shu.	100	Kwangtung.	Canton.	1862, Aug.	N'kwang.
" "	12 1/2	Sung A saw.	100	do	" Ningpo.	1863, May	Ningpo.
" "	14 1/2	Ho A chun.	100	Kwangtung.	Canton, Fokien.	1861, July	Sweow.
" "	11 1/2	Chew Tiam Eok.	100	Singapore.	Fokien, Canton, Ningpo.	1864, "	Tamsui.
" "	16 1/2	W. Munaw.	90	Malacca.	" " "	1859, Oct.	Shanghai.
" "	14 1/2	Tai Tze king.	90	Kwangtung.	Canton.	1861, June	Tientsin.
" "	14 1/2	Leang Atoem.	90	do	" Ningpo.	" Aug.	Shanghai.

Source: *Service List*, 2nd Issue (1876), p. 11.
Figure 2: The 2nd-Issue Service List of 1876 with Date of First Appointment

⁵ The Statistical Department separated its publications into seven series, namely (1) Statistical Series; (2) Special Series; (3) Miscellaneous Series; (4) Service Series; (5) Office Series; and (6) Inspectorate Series. See IG Circular No. 179, 2 February 1882, *Tongling Quanbian*, vol. 2, 381. In 1882, the 7th series, entitled ‘Customs Publications Not Included in Any of the Foregoing Series’ had not inaugurated yet.
⁶ Hart Circular No. 179, 2 February 1882, *Tongling Quanbian*, vol. 2, 382. For the Statistical Department, also see CHANG, Chihyun,

If we take the Chinese staff for example, we could reconstruct the recruitment of Chinese staff from 1854-76 during which there was no *Service List*.

Figure 3: The Chinese Clerks, 1854-1876

This, however, needs to note that two factors would jeopardize the accuracy of the *Service Lists*. Firstly, there was no record about whether or not a staff member was retired or diseased. Thus, ‘the recruits of the year’ and ‘the sum of employees’ can be mistaken. Secondly, the *Service List* of each year includes the staff member by 31st July of the year, so if a member was enrolled in the CMCS from 1st August to 31st December, he would not be listed in the *Service List* of the year. For instance, the 2nd-Issue *Service List* of 1876 listed 80 Chinese Clerks but Cheong A Kam, Leung Chim Fung and Li A Tai were all enrolled in December 1876. Thus, the three Clerks were not listed in the 2nd-Issue *Service List* of 1876.

From 1875-1882, the 1st-8th Issue *Service Lists* were put as an appendix to the *Annual Report on Trade* until 1882. However, since 1882, the Statistical Department launched a full-scale publication project and this changed the arrangement of the *Service List*. In 1882, Hart instructed the Statistical Department to compile the ‘Customs publications’ and categorized the publications into six series.⁵ The *Service Lists* were put in the 4th series, the ‘Service Series’, which would ‘comprise all publications of a service nature prepared for issue to, and use by, members of the service generally.’ Hart particularly emphasized that ‘Publications of the Service Series are neither for sale nor for general distribution; they are to be issued gratis, and – the ‘*Service List*’ excepted – to the members of the service only.’⁶

“Zhongguo Haiguan Zaocechu yu Zhongyang Tongji Zhidu, 1959-1911” (The Statistical Department of the Inspectorate General of Customs and the Statistical System of the Central Government, 1859-1911), in Wu Songdi ed., *Haiguan Wenxian yu Jindai Zhongguo Yanjiu Xueshu Lunwenji* (The Historiography of the CMCS and the Modern Chinese Studies) (Guilin: Guangxi Normal University Press, 2018).

The *Service Lists* then became a rather confidential publication, though not as confidential as the Inspectorate Series. The 9th-Issue *Service List* of 1883 started to have an issue number for the *Service Series*. The *Service Lists* as an open data as an appendix to the *Annual Report on Trade* was open in 1882. In 1883, the 9th-Issue *Service List* became an independent publication.

Figure 4(a): The *Service Lists* as Appendix from 1876-1882 and the Ones of the *Service Series* from 1883-1948; and (b) The *Service Lists* as appendix, 1876-1882

Figure- 4(b) - The *Service List* put in the *Service Series* in 1883

2.2 The English and Chinese Versions

From 1875-1890, the *Service Lists* did not have Chinese versions and only had the Chinese names of the staff members and the names of the departments and sections. Until 1891, the Chinese version was published entitled *Xinguan Timinglv* (*Service List for the New Customs*).

Figure 5(a) - The English Version of the 17th-Issue *Service List*

Figure 5(a) - The Chinese Version of the 17th-Issue *Service List*

These English and Chinese versions were published from 1891-1907. Probably because Robert Hart left China in 1908, the 34th-Issue *Service List* of 1908 changed back to the pre-1890 style and this style remained the same till 1940.

Although the 1891-1907 *Service Lists* with the equivalent Chinese version did provide researchers with an explicit list for translation. However, the inconsistency of translation between the 1891-1907 *Service Lists* and the other ones also has caused confusions and this would be discussed in the 3.2 section.

2.3 The Wartime Service Lists

Since the outbreak of the Second Sino-Japanese War in July 1937, all Custom Houses throughout China, excluding the ones in Manchuria, were still under the control of IG Frederick Maze at the Shanghai Inspectorate. However, the outbreak of the Pacific War separated the CMCS into the Chungking Inspectorate under Chiang Kai-shek and the Kishimoto Hirokichi Inspectorate under Wang Jingwei.⁷ Thus, during the Second Sino-Japanese War, there were three

⁷ See Chang Chihyun “Fenlie de Zhongguo yu Tongyi de Haiguan: Meilehe yu Wangjingwei Zhengfu, 1940-1941” (Separated China and Unified CMCS: Frederick Maze and the Wang Jingwei Government, 1940-1941); in Zhou Huimin ed., *Guojifa de Quanshi yu Yunyong* (The

Interpretations and Application of International Law) (Taipei: National Cheng-Chi University Press, 2012), 113-148.

Inspectorates and three editorial styles of their respective *Service Lists*.

Figure 5(a) - The 70th-Issue Kishimoto *Service List* of 1944

Figure 6(b) - The 71st-Issue Chungking *Service List* of 1945

The complications of the wartime *Service Lists* became more serious since the outbreak of the Pacific War. Since December 1941, the two Inspectorates issued their own *Service Lists* at the same time. The Kishimoto Inspectorate compiled 3 issues from 1942-1944 and the Chungking 2 issues from 1944-1945.

⁸ For Kishimoto’s reforms on the personnel system from 1942-1945, see Chang Chihyun and Jiang Shuiyao, “Niccyyu sensoki ni okeru cyugoku kaikan souzeimushi Kishimoto Hirokichi” (Kishimoto Hirokichi: The Inspector-General of the Chinese Maritime Customs Service during the Second Sino-Japanese War), *Toyo Gakuho* 103, 1 (2021), 1-28.

Figure 7(a) - The 1st-Issue *Service List* of 1956 in Taiwan

The issue numbers were the same but there were three points noteworthy: 1) the Chinese titles were almost identical but the Chungking one was the ‘provisional’ one; 2) the personnel structures were different;⁸ and 3) the end day for enrollment were different.⁹ The reason why the Chungking Inspectorate named its *Service List* as *Provisional Service List* and the Kishimoto one just named it *Service List* was that the former believed that staying at Chungking was a provisional status and the latter believed that it inherited the tradition and legacy of the Maze Inspectorate.

2.4 The Postwar *Service List*

After WWII, the CMCS was reunified so the Statistical Department resumed its publication of the 74th-Issue *Service List* of 1948. After the Civil War, the Taipei Inspectorate resumed the publication of the *Service List* in 1955.

From 1875-1955, the English title of all *Service Lists* remained the same but the Chinese titles actually varied, such as 1) Xinguan Timinlu; 2) Haiguan Zhiyuanlu; 3) Haiguan Zhiyuan Linshi Timinlu; and 4) Haiguan Zhiyuan Timinglu.

Figure 7(a) - The 1st-Issue *Service List* of 1956 in Taiwan

⁹ Chang Chihyun and Jiang Shuiyao, “Niccyyu sensoki ni okeru cyugoku kaikan souzeimushi Kishimoto Hirokichi” (Kishimoto Hirokichi: The Inspector-General of the Chinese Maritime Customs Service during the Second Sino-Japanese War), *Toyo Gakuho* 103, 1 (2021), 1-28.

Figure 8(b) - The 1st-Issue *Service List* of 1956 in Taiwan

3. The Service Lists' Issues

As the publication of Service Lists had launched since 1875, the style of Service Lists varied significantly throughout the seven decades. This section aims to disclose the three issues needed to be resolved before setting up the online database.

3.1 Rank and Post

The first confusion was that 'Commissioner' and 'Deputy Commissioner' could be a rank and a post respectively. The post could be more confusing if a staff member with Assistant rank was appointed head or deputy of a Custom House:

Table 1: The English-Chinese Translations for Post Titles

Post in English	Post in Chinese	Explanation
Acting Commissioner	署理稅務司	A staff member with Deputy Commissioner rank was appointed head of a Custom House and he would become Commissioner in the near future.
Acting Deputy Commissioner	署副稅務司	A staff member with Assistant rank was appointed deputy of a Custom House
Deputy Commissioner in Charge	護理稅務司	A staff member with Deputy Commissioner rank was appointed head of a Custom House and he would not become Commissioner in the near future.
Assistant-in-Charge	代理稅務司	A staff member with Assistant rank was appointed head of a Custom House

For instance, H. J. Fisher was Assistant-in-charge of the Tamsui Custom House but his rank was 1st Assistant B.

Source: *Service List*, 9th Issue (1883), 3 & 7

Figure 9: H. J. Fisher's Post and Rank in the the 9th-Issue *Service List* of 1883

In short, all staff members had a rank but not everyone had a post.

3.1 Translations

There are three problems while translating the *Service Lists*: 1) the changes of translation throughout different *Service Lists*; 2) the switches of translations throughout different *Service Lists*; and 3) the mistakes in one *Service List*.

3.2.1 The changes of translation throughout different *Service Lists*

The first problem is not a mistake made by the Statistical Department and it was just an evolution from literary to modern Chinese language. For instance, Private Secretary was translated into *Lushisi* before 1912 but it became *Mishu Fushuiwusi*. Clerks was *Gongshi* before 1929 but became *Shuiwuyuan* after 1929 and Tidewaiter was *Jinzishou* then became *Jichayuan*, etc.

圖	歷年	到初	發	名姓
司務稅關				
水漢	年八	光緒	年九	德夏
案	二十	七	光緒	德夏
昌宜	二十	六	光緒	德夏
假	三十	年一	光緒	德夏
博江	"	年一	光緒	德夏
假	"	年三	光緒	德夏
"	"	年四	光緒	德夏
同	四十	年六	光緒	德夏
專	"	年七	光緒	德夏
假	"	年八	光緒	德夏
專	六十	"	光緒	德夏
假	"	"	光緒	德夏
專	七十	"	光緒	德夏

Name	Nationality	Date of Appointment	Date of Appointment to present Rank	Station
DEPUTY COMMISSIONERS.				
F. Hirth†	German	1876, June	1882, April	Tientsin.
James W. Carrall†	British	1868, August	1882, August	Chafes.
G. d'Armas†	French	1869, Nov.	1886, April	Ichang.
M. E. Towell†	British	1861, June	1882, June	"
H. M. Hillier†	"	1874, August	"	Shanghai.
W. F. Spilney†	American	1874	"	"
H. B. Morse†	"	"	Nov.	"
M. Boyd Eredon†	British	1880, July	1888, April	"
W. N. Morehouse†	American	1868, April	1882, June	Foochow.
T. E. Cooker†	British	1869, June	"	Canton.
T. Fry†	French	1874, April	"	October.
F. S. Urwin†	British	1868, Sept.	1890, July	Canton.
F. Seljoh†	Norwegian	"	Sept.	"
P. O. von Mollendorff††	German	1869, October	1891, April	Shanghai.
PRIVATE SECRETARY, I.G.				
Edwin Ludlow	British	1880, Sept.	1882, October	Peking.

Name	Nationality	Date of Appointment	Date of Appointment to present Rank	Station
DEPUTY COMMISSIONERS—Cont.				
關稅務司				
Cross, A. W.†	British	1869, Aug.	1911, April	Shanghai.
Richardson, J. W.†	"	1888, Sept.	1912	Peking.
Loyal, L. A.†	"	1886, Oct.	"	"
Currie, R. A.†	"	"	"	Yokoh.
Pereboom, D.†	French	1876	"	Tientsin.
Wakefield, C. E. S.†	British	1886	"	Changsha.
PRIVATE SECRETARY, I.G.				
Richardson, J. W.	British	1888, Sept.	1910, Sept.	Peking.

Source: Service List, 17th Issue (1891), 5
Source: Service List, 38th Issue (1912), 7

Figure 10: Private Secretary's Translations

Name	Nationality	Date of Appointment	Date of Appointment to present Rank	Station
ASSISTANTS-IN-CHARGE				
代理稅務司				
Waldson, F. E.	British	1894, May	1908, April	Nankow.
Lozano, J. W.	Portuguese	1888, April	"	Kongkong.
Pierrat Dautels, H.	French	1896, Nov.	"	Szechuan.
Hedgecock, R. F. C.†	British	1898, May	"	Loyde.

Name	Nationality	Date of Appointment	Date of Appointment to present Rank	Station
DEPUTY COMMISSIONERS IN CHARGE				
代理稅務司				
Shaw, N. H. M.†	British	1907, April	1919, Oct.	Shanghai.
Acting Deputy Commissioners in Charge, at intervals				
暫行代理稅務司				
Morison, M.	Japanese	1909, Sept.	1917, May	Elowah.
Assistant-in-Charge				
副稅務司				
Lay, A. G. H.	British	1910, Dec.	1911, March	Tientsin.
Waldson, A. A.†	British	1910, June	"	Kingchow.
Deputy Commissioners				
副稅務司				
Williams, C. A. S.†††	British	1903, Nov.	1923, April	Peking.
Mann, F. H.†	Dutch	1904, June	1924	"
Shaw, N. H. M.†††	British	1907, April	"	Shanghai.
Wilding, H. St. J.†	"	1904, June	"	"
Cassell, J. T.†	"	1906, April	1906	Wakow.
Kurematsu, Y.†	Japanese	1901, May	1907	Ichang.
Wakatsuki, R.†	"	1907, Aug.	1908	Szechuan.
Pfichardt, R.†	"	1913, May	"	Shanghai.
Schlegelstein, N. H.†	British	1901, June	1909, April	Shanghai.
Wilkes, A. G.†	British	1906, Oct.	"	"
Alkattan, V.†	Japanese	1907, April	"	"
Mandeville, H. G.†	British	1910, Feb.	"	Shanghai.
Lowder, H. G.†	"	1908	"	"
Jordan, K. F.†	British	1911, March	"	Kingchow.

Source: Service List, 35th Issue (1909), 5 & Service List, 47th Issue (1931), 4.

Figure 11: The Chinese Translation for Assistant-in-charge

3.2.2 The switches of translations throughout different Service Lists

The second problem is quite different. For instance, the post of Assistant-in-Charge was translated into *Daili Shuiwusi* in the 35th-Issue *Service List* of 1909 but after it became *Huli Shuiwusi* in the 47th-Issue of *Service List* of 1931 and Deputy Commissioner in Charge became *Daili Shuiwusi*. This is probably not a mistake made by the Statistical Department and the post of Assistant-in-charge was then translated into *Huli Shuiwusi* henceforth, but I have not found out any reason why the Department made this revision.

3.2.3 The mistakes in one Service List

The third question was likely a mistake made by the Statistical Department. For instance, Harbours Staff was translated into *lichuanting* on page iii of the 17th-Issue *Service List* of 1891; but it then became *lichuanchu* on page 80 and *lichuanting* became Harbour Master's Chinese translation.

華洋人員總數			
內洋 華洋 四百九十七 人	外洋 華洋 三百九十三 人	海峽 華洋 四百八十 人	以上 華洋 一千三百七十二 人
船政 處 華洋 二百七 人	船政 處 華洋 一百六十五 人	船政 處 華洋 六十二 人	以上 華洋 四百九十七 人
京師 五 人	粵省 一 人	以上 六 人	以上 華洋 一千三百七十二 人
統計	華洋 一千三百七十二 人	以上 六 人	以上 華洋 一千三百七十二 人

船政處				
巡工司	理船廠	指泊所	供事	信旗吏
一員	一員	一員	一員	三名
巡江吏	六名			

姓名	籍貫	到初	離末	圖
畢士	英	同治七年	光緒六年	江門
...

Source: *Service List*, 17th Issue (1891), iii & 80
Figure 12: The Mistranslation of “Harbours” and “Harbour Master”

3.3 The Three Inspectorates at Wartime

The Secretaries’ translations during the Second Sino-Japanese War were another issue. Because the three wartime Inspectorates were under three different governments, the three IGs had to stick to different translating policies in order to adapt to their respective personnel structures. The Chief, Financial and Chinese Secretaries’ Chinese translations were almost identical but all the other Secretaries’ translations were completely inconsistent.

Table 2: The English-Chinese Translations for Three Wartime Inspectorate General of Customs

1940 Maze Inspectorate	1943 Kishimoto Inspectorate	1945 Chungking Inspectorate
------------------------	-----------------------------	-----------------------------

Chief Secretary	總務科稅務司	總務處長	總務科稅務司
Financial Secretary	財務科稅務司	財務處長	財務科稅務司
Chinese Secretary	漢文科稅務司	漢文處長	漢文科稅務司
Staff Secretary	銓鈞科稅務司	人事處長	人事科稅務司
Tariff Secretary	審權科稅務司	稅則處長	審權科稅務司
Preventive Secretary	緝私科稅務司	緝私處長	查緝科稅務司
Audit Secretary	會計科稅務司	審計處長	計核科稅務司
Personal Secretary	機要科稅務司	秘書處長	秘書室稅務司
Statistical Secretary	統計科稅務司	統計處長	統計科稅務司

As English was the working language of the CMCS, all these translation issues can be evitable if the database is purely English. However, this would make the Chinese academic world less convenient. More importantly, without an adequate understanding of the Chinese translation issues, historians might not understand how the Chinese governments had been endeavoring to regulate the CMCS and fitting it into its own bureaucracy.

4. Previous Studies on the Service Lists

Both western and Chinese historian have been well aware of the importance of the Service Lists but the complete set has always been the main obstacle for everyone. The western and Mainland Chinese historians have taken two different methods respectively to explore the research value of which.

4.2 Mainland Chinese Historians’ Studies

As John Fairbank endeavored to push forward the “Hart Industry” and to edit Robert Hart’s diaries and correspondence in the 1970s,¹⁰ western historians paid less attention to the studies of *Service Lists*. Chen Shiqi was the first historian who started to investigate the *Service Lists* and attempted to reorganize the *Service Lists* for new results.¹¹ In order to help readers to understand the CMCS personnel system, he also edited several research guides.¹² Zhan Qinghua continued Chen’s research course and recalculated the staff members’ fluctuation from 1875-1948 and analyzed their spatial allocations from 1891-1910.¹³ However, Chen’s and Zhan’s research were purely based on the *Service Lists* so they tracked the staff members’ transfer and promotion records as this manner is how the *Service*

¹⁰ For the Hart Enterprise, see Chihyun Chang, “Sir Robert Hart and the Writing of Modern Chinese History”, *International Journal for Asian Studies* (2020) 17: 109-26.

¹¹ Chen Shiqi, “Lun Jindai Zhongguo Haiguan de ‘Guojixing’ he Yangyuan Tongzhi de Yanbian” (The Studies on the Chinese Maritime Customs’ Cosmopolitanism and the Evolution of the Foreign Staff’s Rule), *Research in Chinese Economic History* 1 (1987): 129-146.

¹² Chen Shiqi, *Zhongguo Jindai Haiguan Changyong Ciyu Ying-Han Duzhao Baodian* (The English-Chinese Dictionary for the

Terminologies of the Chinese Maritime Customs Service) (Beijing: The Customs Publisher, 2002). Also see Sun Xiufu ed., *Jindai Zhongguo Huayang Jigou Yiming Daquan* (The Complete Guide for Sino-Foreign Institution in Modern China) (Beijing: The Customs Publisher, 2003)

¹³ Zhan Qinghua, *Quanjuehua Shiye: Zhongguo Haiguan Yangyuan yu Zhongxi Wenhua Chuanbo, 1854-1950* (A Globalization Perspective of Foreign Staff in the Chinese Maritime Customs Service and Transcultural Communication between East and West, 1854-1950) (Beijing: The Customs Publisher, 2008)

Lists were compiled. However, Sun Xiufu has changed this manner and compiled his work in accordance with the Custom Houses with alphabetical order. Then Sun's research demonstrated a clearer sense of the staff members' spatial allocations.¹⁴ But after this wave, the Chinese historians have paid less attention to the *Service Lists* for almost two decades. Recently, Zhao Yue has taken another aspect, the *Customs Gazette*, to investigate the staff members' transferring records from 1865-1913, instead of the *Service Lists*. He also has provided an index and glossary for looking up names. This is the first attempt to verify the validity of *Service Lists*.

In sum, the Mainland Chinese historians realize the importance of the *Service Lists*, and the necessity to reorganize which. All the aforesaid research attempts are still characterized with traditional historiography but these reorganized results only cover a part of the *Service Lists* because human beings' brains cannot process the complete set of *Service Lists*. The fundamental difficulty to utilize the *Service Lists* for historical personnel research remains the same. Thus, a complete database is utterly needed for an advanced investigation.

4.2 Cambridge-Bristol Offline Database

As Hans van de Ven and Robert Bickers started their CMCS project in 2002, funded by the British Arts and Humanities Research Council and the Taiwanese Chiang Ching-kuo Foundation. They established 1) a database for the 56,000 files, 2) a database for the trade returns, and 3) a database for the 22000 CMCS staff members. The staff database is as follow:

The database for staff members was the first attempt to build up a database. This database had 14 attributes: 1) English Surname, 2) English Forename, 3) Simplified Chinese Name, 4) Traditional Chinese Name, 5) Nationality, 6) Birthplace (only for Chinese employees), 7) Date of First Appointment, 8) Position of First Appointment, 9) Service Branch, 10) Port of 1st Appointment, 11) Date Withdraw, 12) Port Withdrawal, 13) Position on Withdrawal, and 14) Mode of Withdrawal.

This was a complete database for all staff members from 1854-1950 but this design of database then neglected all the changes throughout all *Service Lists*, such as a employees' transferring and promotion records. Thus, this database has the following four issues: 1) the working language is English, 2) there is no spatial attributes, 3) there is no temporal attributes as it only has dates of entry and withdrawal, and 4) there is no department and section information.

ID	Surname	Forename	Chinese nat.	Chinese nat.	Nation	Birthplace	Date of 1 st Appointment	Service Branch	Port of 1 st Appointment	Date of Withdrawal	Position on Withdrawal
2694					Japanese			Labour Staff		1942/Jul	Tientsin (on probation)
2694					Japanese			Labour Staff		1942/Jul	Tientsin (on probation)
15012A	Sun	A Sun			Siamese	1899/Jun	Watchman (on probation)			1905/Jan	Swatow
5707A	St	J.A. van			Belgian	1883/Apr	Postal Clerk			1914/Jan	C.U.L.
15437	Ans	C.			American	1903/Oct	Watchman			1904/Mar	Shanghai
5099	Abbot	H.	阿柏德	阿柏德	British	1919/Apr	Probationary Tidewater			1941/Dec	Shanghai
77	Abbot	J.			British	1861/Aug	Clerk			1863/Aug	
194	Abbot	J.			British	1864/Oct	Tidewater			1870/Apr	1st Class Tidewater
194	Abbot	J.			British	1869/Oct	River Police Constable			1870/Apr	River Police Constable
3570	Abbot	R.J.			British	1862/Jun	4th Assistant			1882/Apr	On leave
2620	Abbot	Ronald	阿柏德	阿柏德	British	1919/Apr		Labour Staff		1950/Jan	Deputy Commissioner
7037	Abbot	N.A.			Russian	1916/Apr	Local Watcher			1919/Jan	Local Watcher
7038	Abbot	N.A.			Russian	1908/Jan	Superintendy Watcher			1918/Dec	In
179	Abbot	P.H.			British	1890/Nov	Superintendy Watcher			1897/Apr	Canon
198	Abbot	P.H.			British	1898/Mar	Station Watcher, B			1899/Jun	Lappa
430	Abbot	Abel	阿伯德	阿伯德	British	1900/Mar	Superintendy Watcher			1900/Dec	Shanghai
430	Abbot	Abel	阿伯德	阿伯德	British	1900/Mar	Superintendy Watcher			1945/Aug	Superintendy Watcher
2698	Abc	Masahiro			Japanese	1916/Oct	Local Watcher			1921/May	Shanghai
2797	Abc	Yoshiaki			Japanese	1940/Oct				1945/Aug	Shanghai
15740	Abel	Emil			Japanese	1905/Oct	Probationary Assistant			1924/Jan	Shanghai
195	Abel	Emil			British	1873/Jun	3rd Class Tidewater			1873/Sep	3rd Class Tidewater
694	Abel	A.H.H.			British	1905/Oct	Probationary Assistant			1918/Jun	Canon
17655	Abraham	P.			Spanish	1906/Jul	1st Watcher			1907/Apr	Shanghai
1760	Abraham	C.	阿伯拉罕	阿伯拉罕	Norwegian	1902/Mar	Probationary Tidewater			1930/Aug	Tientsin
2628	Abc	B.S.	阿兰慕夫	阿兰慕夫	Russian	1923/Mar	Probationary Tidewater			1930/Jan	Tientsin
5088	Abc	C.	阿兰慕夫	阿兰慕夫	Russian	1925/Oct	4th Assistant, B			1930/Jan	Tientsin
5744	Abc	Wiles	阿兰慕夫	阿兰慕夫	British	1888/Jun	4th Assistant, B			1924/Jan	London
6515	Abc	G.E.H.	阿兰慕夫	阿兰慕夫	British	1912/Sep	4th Assistant, B			1917/May	Shanghai
6514	Abc	John	阿兰慕夫	阿兰慕夫	British	1873/Jun	4th Assistant, B			1916/Oct	Shanghai
6514	Abc	J.	阿兰慕夫	阿兰慕夫	British	1873/Jun	4th Assistant, B			1916/Oct	Shanghai

Figure 13: The Cambridge-Bristol Staff Database

5. Online Database

From 2006-2010, the author was working on the staff database and trying to utilize this database for the studies of the Chinese staff but this database was not the best solution, so the author has come up with a set of plans for a new online database, and the author sets up four goals 1) retain the *Service Lists*' transferring and promoting records for every staff member, 2) easy to generate visual results, 3) allow different participants to type in the records as the data is vast, and 4) avoid rebuild another database. In order to achieve the four goals, the information of all staff members should be categorized into two sheets, namely the fixed and unfixed information.

5.1 Fixed Information

The Service List has 10 kinds of fixed information: 1) English first name, 2) English surname, 3) Chinese first name, 4) Chinese surname (it is however difficult to identify a foreign employee's Chinese surname as some of them had four-character names so their surname is the first two characters 複姓 but these two characters are not

¹⁴ Sun Xiufu ed., *Zhongguo Jindai Haiguan Gaoji Zhiyuan Nianbiao* (Chronological Table of High Ranking Staffs of the Chinese Maritime

Customs Service in Modern China) (Beijing: The Customs Publisher, 2004).

a Chinese 複姓),15 5) entry year, 6) nationality or birth province (some Chinese employees were born in Hong Kong, Macao and Malacca), 7) spoken languages and dialects, 8) Chinese or Foreign, 9) Department and 10) section, and it is necessary to add the 11th kind of fixed information, which is not in the Service List or the previous database, i.e. citation (page number, issue number of Service Lists) for users' reference.

Among the aforesaid 11 kinds of fixed information, only the 9th and the 10th would have changed occasionally, and the other 9 kinds only changed very few times. These changes are 1) foreign employees changed their Chinese surname and first name, such as 薄郎 (probably it implies 薄幸郎君, a ungrateful husband or lover) to 博朗 (scholarly and frank), 2) reenter the CMCS after retirement, such as 赤谷由助, and 3) change the nationality as he tried to avoid to treated as prisoner of war, such as British First Examiner A F. Gutteridge¹⁶ changed his nationality to Portugal and renamed F. Guttirez.¹⁷ But these three kinds of cases are quite rare. The aforesaid most of the fixed information would allow as to build up a 'Fixed Personal Information Database' as follow:

Figure 14: The “Fixed Personal Information Database” Interface

A well-established 'Fixed Personal Information Database' can guarantee a successful temporal 'Unfixed Personal Information Database'.

5.2 Unfixed Information

Every year all staff members' three attributes would change. The three attributes were 1) Custom House, 2) Rank and 3) Post (not everyone had a post). When typing in the English surname, it would show the employees' information who have already been set up in the 'Fixed Personal Information Database' and the other fixed information would automatically appear in the grey blanks.

¹⁵ The Service Lists did not use simplified Chinese characters so this online database does not have any attributes for simplified Chinese users.
¹⁶ *Service List*, Issue 66 (1940), 84, 227.

Figure 15: The “Unfixed Personal Information Database” Interface

Then we can fill in the blanks for Custom House, Rank and Post, and the longitude and latitude of the Houses, and the English names of which are all fixed in the system.

In other words, the construction of this CMCS staff database is separated into two steps: 1) the 'Fixed Personal Information Database' and 2) the annual temporal database. Although it looks more complicated, it exactly can avoid typing errors as the 'Fixed Personal Information Database' cannot be changed accidentally. However, the only problem is that the annual temporal database has to be set up year by year and this is very time consuming. Thus, the solution is to have copy the previous Service List as the changes of each year's Service List are only a few. This is the best way to save our time to set up in the annual temporal database.

Figure 16: The “Unfixed Personal Information Database” Interface for Choosing Custom House, Rank and Post.

¹⁷ Benjamin Geoffrey White, “Question of Principle with Political Implications” – Investigating Collaboration in the Chinese Maritime Customs Service, 1945–1946,” *Modern Asian Studies* 44, 3 (2010), 526.

姓名	國籍	出生年	職稱	中文職稱	中文職稱	中文職稱	職稱
Pty	英	1857	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦
Harner	德	1859	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦
Hart	德	1859	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦
Lud	德	1859	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦
Hankow	德	1859	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦
Wah	德	1859	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦
Fisher	德	1861	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦
Mosley	德	1861	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦	總辦

Figure 17: The Service List Combined the Fixed and Unfixed Personal Information with the Function to Copy the Previous Year's Service List

This function allows us to focus on two tasks: 1) add the newly recruited employees, and 2) pick up the employees who moved to new Custom Houses, had promotions, and new posts. This can be much more efficient.

In-door.	Date of Appointment to present rank.	Years previously served.	Name.	Nationality.	Date of first Appointment.	Station.
FOURTH ASSISTANTS: B.—Cont.						
	1883, Jan.	—	T. D. Moorhead ¹	British	1883, Jan.	London.
	July	—	A. E. von Rosshorn	Austrian	July	Peking.
	"	—	C. T. Bowring	British	"	Hankow.
	"	—	A. H. Harris	"	"	Peking.
	"	—	J. O. P. Bland	"	"	Swatow.
	"	—	A. H. Stigden	"	"	London.
	1884, April	—	R. H. Mazo	"	1884, April	Shanghai.
	"	—	R. Markwick	"	"	"

Source: Service List, 9th Issue (1883), 14

Figure 18: The New Recruits to Be Typed into the Database

Combined the fixed and unfixed information, this platform can generate a year by year Service List and then can visualize the yearly changes throughout all Service Lists.

6. Spatio-Temporal GISystem

The combination of 1) the 'Fixed Personal Information Database' and 2) the annual temporal database can demonstrate its visualization by GISystem easily, and in our project, there are three kinds of visualization: 1) spatial visualization, 2) temporal visualization, and 3) statistical visualization.

6.2 Spatial Visualization

The spatial visualization focuses on the staff members and their Custom Houses on a map of China, Korea and Taiwan, and a pie and chart graphs would appear next to the map.

6.1.1. Visualize All Custom Houses' Staff Members in A Particular Year

Case 1: The Visualization and Charts for All Custom Houses' Staff Members in 1876.

The Shanghai Custom House always had most staff members and the Canton one seconded to it. The third biggest ones were Hankow, Foochow and Amoy, and the fourth one were the Peking Inspectorate, Newchuang, Tientsin, Chinkiang, Kiukiang, Swatow, Tamsui and Takow.

Figure 19: The Pie Graph for the Foreign Assistants in 1876

Figure 20: The Spatial Allocations for the Foreign Assistants in 1876

Before this database, we only could know a Custom House started to operate by its Returns of Trade and/or Reports on Trade. But through all these charts, it can show the Custom Houses' number and we can know when a Custom House started to have new staff members. For instance, 15 Custom House received new members in 1876, 19 ones (all Korean Custom Houses excluded, the Wuhu, Ichang, Wenchow and Pakoi Custom Houses had received new members), and 23 ones (Tamsui and Takow excluded, but Chungking, Kowloon, Lappa, Lungchow, Mengtze, Yatung added) in 1895.

There is another function for comparing the number of members in each Custom Houses. For instance, Shanghai always had most members and Canton seconded to Shanghai. However, the third biggest Houses varied. Three Custom Houses started to receive more members in 1876, five ones in 1886 and seven ones in 1895.

6.1.2 Visualize One Custom House's Staff Members' Nationalities, Birth Province and Rank in One Particular Year

Case 1: The Nationalities for all foreign staff members in the Shanghai Custom House in 1876.

Table 3: The Foreign Assistants at the Shanghai Custom House

海關名	比利時	法國	俄國	美國	英國	華籍	奧地利	瑞士	德國	总计
上海關	1	3	1	4	17	29	1	1	1	58
总计	1	3	1	4	17	29	1	1	1	58

Figure 21: The Bar Graph for the Foreign Assistants' Ranks at the Shanghai Custom House in 1876

The dark green bar is the number of the Custom House and the light green one is the number of the whole CMCS.

6.1.3 Visualize the Multiple Custom Houses and Nationalities in a Particular Year

Case 1: the comparison of all nationalities' staff members between Shanghai, Hankow and Canton in 1876.

Table 4: The Foreign Assistants at the Shanghai, Hankow and Canton Custom Houses

海關名	比利時	法國	俄國	美國	英國	挪威	華籍	奧地利	瑞士	德國	总计
江海關	1	3	1	4	17		29	1	1	1	58
江漢關		1		1	6		3			1	12
粵海關		1		1	7	1	16				26
总计	1	5	1	6	30	1	48	1	1	2	96

This table can show the accurate number for each Custom House's and nationality's staff members.

6.1.4 Visualize the Spatial Allocations of One Nationality's Staff Members on Map and its Pie and Bar Graphs

Case 1: All ranks' Chinese staff's spatial allocations, pie and bar graphs in 1876

Figure 22: The Spatial Allocations for Chinese Clerks in 1876

Figure 23: The Pie Graph for Chinese Clerks in 1876

Figure 24: The Bar Graph for Chinese Clerks’ Ranks at the Shanghai Custom House in 1876

Through these graphs, it is clear that the Shanghai, Canton, Amoy, Swatow, Chinkiang and Tamsui Custom Houses had more Chinese staff members than other Houses in 1876.

Case 2: All ranks’ British staff members’ spatial allocations, pie and bar graphs in 1876.

Figure 25: The Spatial Allocations for British Assistants, Deputy Commissioners and Commissioners in 1876

Figure 26: The Pie Graph for British Assistants, Deputy Commissioners and Commissioners in 1876

Figure 27: The Bar Graph for British Assistants, Deputy Commissioners and Commissioners in 1876

Through the graphs, it shows that the Peking Inspectorate, Kiukiang and Newchuang had more British staff members.

6.1.5 Visualize the Spatial Allocations of One Rank’s Staff Members and its Pie and Bar Graphs.

Case 1: All 4th Assistants’ B 1876 spatial allocations, pie and bar graphs in 1876.

Figure 28: The Pie Graph for 4th Assistants’ B in 1876

Figure 29: The Spatial Allocations for 4th Assistants' B in 1876

Table 5: The French, American, British and Austrian Assistants at the southern Custom Houses

海關名	法國	美國	英國	奧地利	总计
▲					
九江關			1		1
牛莊關			2		2
打狗關		1			1
江海關	2	1	3	1	7
江漢關		1	1		2
廈門關		1			1
寧波關	1				1
鎮江關			1		1
总计	3	4	8	1	16

Through these graphs, it shows that the Inspectorate still tended to recruit British candidates but the recruitment scale was limited in 1876.

6.1.6 Visualize the Spatial Allocations and Numbers of Multiple Rank's Staff Members in One Particular Year

Case 1: The 4th Assistants' A and B spatial allocations, pie and bar graphs in 1876.

Figure 30: The Pie Graph for 4th Assistants' A and B

Figure 31: The Spatial Allocations for 4th Assistants' A and B

Table 6: The Belgian, Hungarian, French, American, British and Austrian Assistants in China

海關名	比利時	匈牙利	法國	美國	英國	奧地利	总计
▲							
九江關					1		1
牛莊關			1		2	1	4
北京總署			1		1		2
打狗關				1			1
江海關			2	1	3	1	7
江漢關				1	1		2
東海關					1		1
津海關			1		1		2
廈門關					1		1
寧波關					1		1
閩海關	1						1
鎮江關					1		1
总计	1	1	5	4	12	2	25

Through the graph, it shows that the Kiukiang Custom House had most 4th Assistants A and B compared to other Houses.

6.2 Statistical Visualization

This statistical visualization uses the square, line, and bar graphs for staff members in a year. This could not demonstrate the spatio-temporal changes over time but this could provide a clear sense of the staff members' numbers in one issue's *Service List*.

6.2.1 Visualize the Square, Line, and Bar Graphs for All Staff Members, Ranks and Nationalities in One Particular Year

Case 1

Figure 32: The Square Graph for All Ranks' Assistants in 1876

Case 2

Figure 33: The Bar Graph for All Nationalities' Assistants and Clerks in 1876

Case 3

Figure 34: The Line Graph for All Nationalities' Assistants and Clerks from 1876-1896

Case 4

Figure 35: The Line Graph for American Assistants' Number from 1876-1896

Case 5

Figure 36: The Line Graph for the Comparison between Chinese and British Staff's Numbers from 1876-1896

Some graphs may demonstrate similar results but users can choose whatever they see fit for their research.

6.2.2 Visualize the Square Graph for the Number of One Nationality's Staff Members

Case 1 : The square graph for all ranks' British staff in 1876 (the darker part is the percentage of British staff and the number indicate how many British staff members held the rank).

Figure 37: The Square Graph for the British Assistants in 1876

6.2.3 Visualize the Bar Graph for Multiple Nationalities and Ranks' Staff Members
Case 1

Figure 38: The Bar graph for all nationalities' 4th Assistants A and B in 1876

6.2.4 Visualize One Rank's Staff Members of All Nationalities
Case 1

Figure 39: The Line Graph for All Nationalities' 4th Assistants B from 1876-1896
Case 2

Figure 40: The Line Graph for All British 4th Assistants B from 1876-1896
Case 3

Figure 41: The Line Graph for French, American and German 4th Assistants B from 1876-1896

6.3 Temporal Visualization

This temporal visualization demonstrates staff members' transfers on the map of China, Korea and Taiwan.

6.3.1 Visualize One Nationality's Staff Members Transfers during a Period

Case 1: All German Staff Members' Transfers from 1875-1895.

This shows that the German staff members most likely concentrated at the Shanghai. The Peking Inspectorate, and Canton seconded to Shanghai. The third concentrated ones were Tientsin, Ningpo. In addition, it also shows that no German staff member had served at the Wuhu, Hankow, Lungchow, Mengtze and Busan Custom Houses.

Figure 42: All German Staff Members' Transfers from 1875-1895

Case 2: All French Staff Members' Transfers from 1875-1895.

This shows that the French staff members most likely concentrated at the Shanghai. The Peking Inspectorate, and Canton seconded to Shanghai. The third concentrated ones were Chinkiang, Kiukiang and Wenchow. In addition, it also shows that no French staff member had served at the Tientsin Wuhu, Chungking, Kowloon, Kiungchow, Yunsen and Busan Custom Houses

Figure 43: All French Staff Members' Transfers from 1875-1895

Through these two maps, they show the spatial allocations and concentration of German and French staff members.

6.3.2 Visualize the Transfers of One Nationality's Staff Members in Different Periods

Case 1: The German staff from 1876-1885.

It shows that the German staff mainly served at Shanghai. Tientsin, Foochow and Amoy seconded to them. The third ones were Peking Inspectorate, Swatow, Canton and Takow. In addition, it shows that during this period, they never served at Wuhu, Wenchow, Pakoi, Tamsui and Busan.

Figure 44: The German staff from 1876-1885

Case 2: The German staff from 1886-1895.

It shows that the German staff mainly served at the Peking Inspectorate and Shanghai. Canton, Ningpo seconded to them. The third ones were Tientsin, Chinkiang, Kowloon and Kiungchow. In addition, it shows that during this period, they never served at Chefoo, Wuhu, Hankow, Ichang, Swatow, Lungchow, Mengtze and Busan.

Figure 45: The German staff from 1886-1895

The maps for German staff from 1876-1885 and the one from 1886-1895 show that the German staff concentrated at Shanghai from 1876-1885 and then at Shanghai and Peking Inspectorate from 1886-1895. The second concentrated Houses were Tientsin, Foochow and Amoy during the former period and then became Canton and Ningpo during the latter. In addition, they show that from the German staff had never served at Wuhu, Lungchow, Mengtze and Busn from 1876-1895.

6.3.3 Visualize One Staff Member’s Transfers

Case 1: German Assistant F. Hirth from 1875-1895.

It shows that he only served at Shanghai, Chinkiang, Chungking, Amoy, Kowloon and Tamsui.

Figure 46: German Assistant F. Hirth’s Transfers from 1875-1895

Case 2: German Assistant E. Ohlmer from 1875-1895.

It shows that he only served at Canton, Lappa and Pakoi.

Figure 47: German Assistant E. Ohlmer’s Transfers from 1875-1895

7. Conclusion

This article aims to provide historians who like to study the CMCS staff with a solution: the combination of the ‘fixed personal information, ‘unfixed Personal information’ and the spatio-temporal GISystem. Not only can this solution work on the CMCS staff but also other personnel studies, such as the *Qingdai Jinshenlu Jicheng* (The List for Gentries during the Qing Dynasty). Meanwhile, this article also provides GIS specialists with another thought to design a spatio-temporal platform for similar projects. In addition, it is also different from the previous historical GIS research as the previous pattern was that historians ask a question, set up a database and then a map is then generated by the database. This solution then becomes a new paradigm: one database, multi maps, and then the maps can help us to ask multi questions. A variety of visual demonstrations can help us to be aware of much more phenomena and ask more questions which we could not notice before.

Compared to the Cambridge-Bristol database, this new database has built up a staff list much similar to the original Service Lists. Moreover, the design of two respective “fixed personal information” and “unfixed personal information” guarantees type-error can be avoided to a great degree. Although the design of “fixed personal information” and “unfixed personal information” can be somehow redundant and time-consuming, it seems to the authors that while historians are dealing with a set of materials as vast as the Service Lists, the priority is to avoid repeating labor and mistakes. This is why the authors have come up with an untraditional methods and methodologies. This design of database is particularly applicable to the tracking after a vast number of people with a wide range of geographical locations, salaries, language and dialect skills, etc.

However, this project is still far away from completion. The future plan can mainly be described in four aspects: Firstly, right now, only the foreign Assistants’ and Chinese Clerks’ information from 1875-1895 is in the database. The vast staff members in the Marine Department, especially the Lights, and all the ones in the Postal Department (the scale was even bigger than the CMCS ones) are still waiting for typing into the database. Secondly, a wide range of visualizing details also can be improved, especially the temporal visualization. It would be much clearer if the transfers can show the direction.

Thirdly, some additional skills, certificates and decorations of the staff should be included as well although not everyone had this information.

Fourthly, it should have English and Japanese interfaces. The existence of these issues, however, still cannot deny the very fact that the design of this database and GISystem is probably the only solution for investigating the *Service Lists* and any other similar vast scale personnel records, such as the *Qingdai Jinshenlu Jicheng*. Moreover, this database and GISystem have already helped us to be well aware of the following three interesting clues historians have not noticed yet:

1. The Kiukiang Custom House was the first station Robert Hart liked to place the new recruits from 1876-1895 probably because it was a relatively new station with less tasks.

2. Judging from the transfers of the French and German staff was equally less important from 1876-1895.

3. The Peking Inspectorate's personnel scale was always much smaller than the Shanghai Custom House. This meant the Hart Inspectorate's power was probably much less centralized than the Maze Inspectorate during the 1930s.

There are still many other clues generated by the visualization but to the authors the three clues would lead us to a much better understanding of this cosmopolitan institution in the nineteenth century. With more labor force to the database, this database and GISystem would provide historians with a new tool for institutional and personnel history.

8. References

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